

ADVANCEMENTS IN CONTROL SYSTEMS: UNDERSTANDING FOPID CONTROLLERS

Botirov T.V.
Sodiqov B.Q.
Jumabayev E.O.

Tutors of Navoi State Mining University
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Abstract: Control systems play a crucial role in regulating various processes in industries ranging from manufacturing to aerospace. As technology advances, so does the need for more sophisticated control algorithms. Fractional-order proportional-integral-derivative (FOPID) controllers have emerged as a promising solution due to their ability to offer improved performance over traditional PID controllers. In this article, we'll delve into the fundamentals of FOPID controllers, their advantages, and their applications in diverse fields.

Keywords: Control systems, PID controller, FOPID controller,

Fundamentals of FOPID Controllers: FOPID controllers extend the classical PID control framework by introducing fractional calculus into the proportional, integral, and derivative terms. Unlike traditional integer-order derivatives and integrals, fractional-order derivatives and integrals consider non-integer orders, allowing for more flexibility and better handling of complex systems.

The general form of a FOPID controller is represented as:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \frac{1}{t^\alpha} \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + K_d \frac{d^\beta e(t)}{dt^\beta}$$

Where:

- K_p , K_i , and K_d are the proportional, integral, and derivative gains respectively.
- α and β represent the fractional orders of the integral and derivative terms.

Advantages of FOPID Controllers:

1. **Enhanced Robustness:** FOPID controllers exhibit improved robustness compared to traditional PID controllers, especially in systems with uncertainties or time delays.
2. **Better Performance:** The fractional-order nature allows FOPID controllers to handle processes with non-linear dynamics more effectively, leading to superior control performance.
3. **Versatility:** FOPID controllers offer a wider range of tuning options due to the additional fractional-order parameters, enabling finer control adjustments.

Applications of FOPID Controllers:

1. **Industrial Automation:** FOPID controllers find extensive applications in industrial automation processes such as temperature control, pressure regulation, and flow control.
2. **Renewable Energy Systems:** In renewable energy systems like wind turbines and solar power plants, FOPID controllers help optimize power generation and grid integration.
3. **Biomedical Engineering:** FOPID controllers are employed in medical devices such as insulin pumps and drug delivery systems for precise control of dosages.
4. **Robotics:** Robotics applications benefit from FOPID controllers for achieving accurate motion control and trajectory tracking in robotic manipulators and autonomous vehicles.

A Fractional Order Proportional Integral Derivative (FOPID) controller is an extension of the classical PID controller. It involves fractional calculus concepts to introduce fractional orders of differentiation and integration into the controller's transfer function. Here's a general structural scheme of a FOPID controller:

Error Calculation: The error ($e(t)$) is calculated as the difference between the setpoint (SP) and the process variable (PV).

Proportional (P) Term: The proportional term is scaled by the proportional gain (K_p) and the error. In a FOPID controller, this term may be fractional order (e.g., proportional gain of order α).

Integral (I) Term: The integral term accumulates the error over time and is scaled by the integral gain (K_i). In a FOPID controller, this term may also be fractional order.

Derivative (D) Term: The derivative term is the rate of change of the error and is scaled by the derivative gain (K_d). In a FOPID controller, this term may also be fractional order.

Summation: The proportional, integral, and derivative terms are summed together to produce the control output ($U(t)$).

Output Limiting (Optional): Optionally, the control output may be limited to prevent it from exceeding certain bounds.

FOPID controllers represent a significant advancement in control systems engineering, offering improved performance and versatility over traditional PID controllers. With their ability to handle complex dynamics and uncertainties, FOPID controllers have found widespread applications across various industries, contributing to enhanced efficiency and productivity. As research in fractional-order control continues to evolve, we can expect further refinements and innovations in this field, opening up new possibilities for advanced control solutions in the future.

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